

The mechanical and technical ethics in the production in AI generative art

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John Berger, Walter Benjamin, and André Bazin were three influential scholars who wrote extensively about the impact of mechanical and technical reproduction on the arts. In this research paper, we will explore their teachings and examine the ways in which AI generative art relates to their ideas.

John Berger was a British art critic, novelist, and painter who is best known for his 1972 book *Ways of Seeing*. In this book, Berger argued that mechanical reproduction, such as photography and film, had fundamentally changed the way that people saw and interacted with art. According to Berger, mechanical reproduction had made art more accessible to the masses, but it had also diminished the unique qualities of individual works of art.

Walter Benjamin was a German philosopher, cultural critic, and translator who is best known for his 1936 essay *The Work of Art in the Age of Mechanical Reproduction*. In this essay, Benjamin argued that mechanical reproduction had fundamentally changed the way that people experienced art. According to Benjamin, mechanical reproduction had made art more democratic, but it had also diminished its aura, or the sense of uniqueness and authenticity that an original work of art possesses.

André Bazin was a French film critic and theorist who is best known for his books *What is Cinema?* and *The Myth of Total Cinema*. In these books, Bazin explored the impact of technical reproduction, such as sound and color, on the medium of film. According to Bazin, technical reproduction had greatly expanded the expressive possibilities of cinema, but it had also led to a loss of realism and verisimilitude.

In the context of AI generative art, these ideas are particularly relevant. AI generative art is a form of digital art that is created using artificial intelligence algorithms. These algorithms are able to generate original works of art without human input, and the resulting works are often highly unique and unpredictable.

At the same time, AI generative art is also a form of mechanical and technical reproduction. The algorithms used to create these works are based on mathematical formulas and computer code, which are essentially mechanical and technical in nature. As a result, AI generative art is both highly original and highly reproducible.

In this sense, AI generative art can be seen as a continuation of the ideas discussed by Berger, Benjamin, and Bazin. Like mechanical and technical reproduction, AI generative art has made

art more accessible and democratic, but it has also diminished the aura and uniqueness of individual works of art.

In terms of Walter Benjamin's ideas about the aura of a work of art, AI generative art may also challenge our traditional understanding of what it means for a work of art to have an aura. Benjamin argued that the aura of a work of art is derived from its uniqueness and authenticity, and that mechanical reproduction diminishes this aura. However, AI generative art is highly reproducible, and yet it is also highly original and unpredictable. As a result, it is difficult to say whether or not AI generative art has an aura in the traditional sense. This challenges our traditional understanding of the concept of aura, and it forces us to consider the ways in which mechanical reproduction has changed our relationship to art.

Furthermore, AI generative art can be seen as a challenge to the traditional notion of art as a human creation. By relying on algorithms and computer code, AI generative art is created by machines rather than human artists. This raises questions about the role of the artist in the creation of art, and the extent to which art can be considered a uniquely human endeavor.

In conclusion, the teachings of John Berger, Walter Benjamin, and André Bazin are relevant to the study of AI generative art. Their ideas about mechanical and technical reproduction can help us to understand the ways in which AI generative art relates to the tradition of art, and the challenges and opportunities that it presents.

Art has always played a significant role in human culture and society, serving as a means of self-expression, communication, and aesthetic enjoyment. As technology has advanced, the way in which art is created and experienced has also evolved, and AI-generated art is one example of this. In this we will learn how the cult value and exhibition value of traditional oil paintings compare with those of AI generative art, in order to understand how these two art forms differ and how they might be valued by viewers.

The cult value of a traditional oil painting refers to its cultural or historical significance, while the exhibition value refers to its aesthetic appeal or the extent to which it is considered to be a "good" or "successful" work of art. Traditional oil paintings often have a strong cult value because they are associated with specific artists or historical periods, and they can convey cultural or symbolic meanings. The exhibition value of traditional oil paintings may be determined by the skill and technique of the artist, the composition and design of the work, or the emotional impact that it has on the viewer.

AI-generated art, on the other hand, may not have the same cult value as traditional oil paintings because it is not typically associated with specific artists or historical periods. However, the exhibition value of AI-generated art can still be evaluated based on similar criteria, such as the skill and innovation of the algorithms used to generate it, the aesthetic appeal of the resulting artworks, and their impact on the viewer.

One argument in favor of the value of AI-generated art is that it can be highly innovative and experimental. AI systems are able to generate art in ways that are not possible for traditional artists, and this can lead to the creation of unique and novel artworks. In addition, AI-generated art can challenge traditional notions of what constitutes "art" by demonstrating that it can be created through algorithms and machine learning. This can make it a valuable way to explore and comment on contemporary society.

In conclusion, the cult value and exhibition value of traditional oil paintings and AI generative art differ in some important ways. While traditional oil paintings are often associated with specific artists or historical periods and can convey cultural or symbolic meanings, AI-generated art may be valued for its innovation, novelty, and ability to challenge traditional notions of art. However, both traditional oil paintings and AI-generated art can be evaluated based on their aesthetic appeal and the impact they have on the viewer. Ultimately, the value of any art form is subjective and will depend on the individual viewer's personal tastes and values.

In relation to AI art, this understanding of ethics raises several questions. Since AI art is created using algorithms and computer code, rather than human photographers, the traditional dynamic of power, possession, and control is disrupted. In AI art, the machine has the power to choose what to create, the possession of the resulting work, and the control over how it is presented to others.

This raises ethical questions about the role of the human artist in the creation of AI art. If the machine is the one that has the power, possession, and control, what is the role of the human artist?

Additionally, Sontag's emphasis on emotion in photography also raises questions about the role of emotion in AI art. Since AI art is created by machines, it is difficult to say whether or not it has the capacity for emotion. However, some AI algorithms are designed to generate art that evokes emotional responses in viewers. In this sense, AI art may have the ability to generate emotional responses in a way that is similar to traditional photography.

Plato's cave allegory, which is found in his book *The Republic*, is a famous metaphor for the way that human perception is limited and flawed. In the allegory, Plato describes a group of people who have been imprisoned in a cave since birth. These people can only see the shadows of objects on the cave wall, and they believe that these shadows are the only reality. However, when one of the prisoners is freed and is able to see the real objects outside of the cave, he realizes that the shadows are only a pale imitation of the real world.

In relation to AI generative art, Plato's cave allegory can be seen as a metaphor for the way that human perception is limited by our preconceived notions of what art is and how it should be created. AI generative art is created using algorithms and computer code, and the resulting works are often highly unique and unpredictable. As a result, these works may challenge our preconceived notions of what constitutes art, and they may force us to consider the limitations of our own perception.

In terms of Susan Sontag's ideas about power, possession, and control in photography, AI generative art can be seen as a disruption of the traditional dynamic between the photographer and the photograph. Since AI generative art is created by algorithms and computer code, rather than human photographers, the machine has the power to choose what to create, the possession of the resulting work, and the control over how it is presented to others. This challenges our traditional understanding of the role of the photographer, and it raises questions about the extent to which art can be considered a human endeavor.

Berger's ideas can help us to understand the ways in which our understanding of these works is shaped by the social and cultural context in which they are created. For example, the fact that AI art is created using algorithms and computer code is a product of the technological context in which it exists. This technology has the potential to change the way that we see and understand art, and it may challenge our traditional notions of what constitutes art and what it means to be an artist.

Furthermore, the fact that AI art is often highly unique and unpredictable may challenge our traditional ways of seeing art. Since AI algorithms are not bound by the same constraints as human artists, they are able to generate works that are highly original and unexpected. This may challenge our assumptions about what art should look like and how it should be experienced.

Overall, the use of AI created artworks can be seen as a continuation of the ideas explored by John Berger in *Ways of Seeing*. These works challenge our traditional ways of seeing art, and they force us to consider the social and cultural context in which they are created. By understanding these ideas, we can gain a deeper appreciation of the unique qualities of AI art and its potential to change the way we see and understand the world around us.

In his writings, André Bazin explored the ways in which the camera and its technical abilities impact the medium of film. In particular, he was interested in the concepts of montage and *mise-en-scène*, which refer to the way that images are composed and arranged within a frame.

In the context of AI, the impact on the role of the camera in relation to these concepts is likely to be significant. AI algorithms are able to analyze and understand the visual elements of a scene, such as the composition, lighting, and color, in a way that is similar to a human filmmaker. This allows AI to generate montage and *mise-en-scène* that is highly sophisticated and complex, potentially surpassing the abilities of human filmmakers.

Furthermore, AI algorithms are able to analyze and understand the emotional content of a scene in a way that is similar to a human filmmaker. This allows AI to generate montage and *mise-en-scène* that is highly effective at evoking emotional responses in viewers. This could potentially challenge traditional notions of what makes a good film and what it means to be a skilled filmmaker.

Overall, the impact of AI on the role of the camera in relation to montage and mise-en-scène is likely to be significant. While AI may not replace human filmmakers entirely, it has the potential to greatly enhance their abilities and challenge traditional notions of what constitutes good filmmaking.

In the context of AI generative art, the concept of technical reproduction can be seen as undergoing a kind of meta-morphosis. AI generative art is created using algorithms and computer code, which are essentially technical and mechanical in nature. As a result, AI generative art is highly reproducible, and yet it is also highly original and unpredictable.

This meta-morphosis of technical reproduction can be seen in the ways in which AI generative art challenges traditional notions of art and creativity. By relying on algorithms and computer code, rather than human artists, AI generative art disrupts the traditional dynamic of artistic creation, and it raises questions about the role of the human artist in the creation of art.

Furthermore, the meta-morphosis of technical reproduction can also be seen in the ways in which AI generative art expands the expressive possibilities of art. By generating highly original and unpredictable works, AI generative art has the potential to challenge our preconceived notions of what art should look like and how it should be experienced.

Overall, the meta-morphosis of technical reproduction in the context of AI generative art can be seen as a continuation and expansion of the ideas discussed by André Bazin. By combining the reproducibility of technical reproduction with the originality and unpredictability of AI, AI generative art has the potential to challenge our traditional notions of art and creativity, and to expand the expressive possibilities of the medium.

The use of artworks as a reference tool for modern artists is a common practice, and it is generally considered to be a legitimate and ethical way to create new art. By looking at the work of other artists, modern artists are able to draw inspiration and ideas, and they are able to create new works that build on the traditions of the past.

However, the use of artworks as a reference tool for AI generative art is more complex, and it raises ethical and legal questions. Since AI algorithms are able to analyze and understand the visual elements of an artwork, they are able to generate new works that are highly similar to the original. In some cases, these generated works may be indistinguishable from the original, and this raises questions about intellectual property and copyright laws.

Agalma is a term that has been used in various contexts, but it is most commonly associated with the ancient Greek concept of a "statue" or "work of art." In the context of AI and generative art, Agalma could refer to an AI-generated artwork that is highly polished and refined, or it could refer to an AI system that is able to create such artworks.

There are a number of different approaches to generating art using AI, and the specific techniques and tools used can vary widely. Some AI systems are designed to generate art from

scratch, using algorithms and machine learning techniques to create original images, sculptures, or other forms of artistic expression. Other AI systems are designed to assist artists in creating art, either by providing suggestions or by automating certain tasks.

It is possible that an AI system could be said to have "Agalma" in the sense that it is able to create highly polished and refined artworks. However, it is important to note that AI is still a tool, and the final product will always depend on the vision and creativity of the human artist or designers who are using it.

Is the human artist simply a facilitator of the machine's creativity?

In terms of copyright laws, the use of artworks as a reference tool for AI generative art may also raise legal issues. If an AI algorithm generates a work that is highly similar to an existing artwork, it may be considered to be a derivative work, and the creator of the AI algorithm may be required to obtain permission from the original artist or to pay a licensing fee. This raises questions about the extent to which AI generated art is subject to existing copyright laws, and it may require further clarification from legal experts.

A further dive into this issue can also be argued using museums which have art by unethical means. AI is also accused of such doings but if we use traditional values of how art is used more as preservation for the future generations and knowledge in how the world was generations prior. We shall now begin about how we should approach this subject.

There is a clear similarity between the collection of art that has been illegally acquired by museums and the use of a set database in AI-generated art in that both involve the appropriation of existing material.

In the case of illegally acquired art, museums may have obtained works of art through theft, looting, or other illicit means. These works of art are often taken from their original contexts and placed in museums, where they may be displayed and studied. This can be problematic because it involves the removal of cultural artifacts from their communities of origin, and it can also deprive these communities of the ability to preserve and protect their own cultural heritage.

AI-generated art, on the other hand, relies on the use of a set database of images, sounds, or other materials that the AI system uses as raw input. The AI system then processes this input and generates new artworks based on it. While this process can be highly creative and innovative, it is also dependent on the material that is fed into the system. This means that AI-generated art is limited by the scope and diversity of the materials in the database, and it can also be influenced by any biases or prejudices that may be present in the data.

Both the collection of illegally acquired art and the use of a set database in AI-generated art involve the appropriation of existing material, and both can raise ethical and cultural concerns. It is important for museums and artists to be mindful of these issues and to consider the ways in which their practices may impact the communities and cultures from which the materials they

use are drawn. However there are a few similarities between the acquisition of art by museums and the use of a set database in AI-generated art:

1. Both involve the collection and organization of materials: Museums collect and organize artworks, while AI systems collect and organize data that is used to generate art.
2. Both can raise ethical and cultural concerns: The acquisition of art by museums can raise concerns about the removal of cultural artifacts from their communities of origin, while the use of a set database in AI-generated art can raise concerns about the impact of biases and prejudices in the data on the resulting artworks.
3. Both can be influenced by external factors: The artworks in museum collections are influenced by the cultural and historical contexts in which they were created, while AI-generated art is influenced by the materials in the set database and the algorithms used to generate it.
4. Both involve the appropriation of existing materials: Museums acquire artworks that have been created by others, while AI-generated art uses existing materials as raw input to create new artworks.

As a result, many artists are beginning to experiment with AI generative art, and they are exploring the potential of this new medium to create innovative and expressive works. This is leading to the development of new artistic movements and styles that are influenced by AI generative art, and it is challenging many of the traditional notions about art that have persisted for centuries.

The creation of AI generative art is leading to the abandonment of many traditional notions about art, just as the creation of photography did in the 19th century .We witness the creation of a tool far beyond our actual pathos and challenging the ethos of human intervention in art , the expanding and infinite expressive possibilities of the medium, AI generative art is paving the way for a new era of artistic expression.